

Integral image algorithm for locally approximate additive log-network

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Abstract

A log-network has been introduced in an earlier version. But, that requires many parameters to learn and can be difficult to explain (and defeats the purpose to some extent). Computationally simple model is required. So, a receptive field based network is being proposed. This has the advantages of being able to use integral images or summed-area tables for both forward pass and backward pass (backpropagation).

Note: The experiments have not been discussed. I am planning to discuss the experiments using a peer reviewed version of this.

1 Introduction

The integral image log-network (IILN) is supposed to work much like a CNN. It is a log-network which doesn't have any complex output. The idea of kernel or filter is the integral image with a window size specified as an input. The kernel or filter itself doesn't "move" throughout the image. But, instead of a dense log-network that connects each input to each output, a spatially relevant set of inputs are used. The hypothesis is that it helps us with explainability (and is much faster computationally). The local approximation theorem applies here.

2 Prior Work

This research uses the idea of Additive Statistically Approximate Distributions (log-network).[1] But, instead of a "dense" network, an integral image version is being proposed to make it explainable and computationally efficient. The integral image or the summed-area tables idea is from a prior research which involves graphics.[3] A modified version of backpropagation is used as log can have unexpected outputs when the input is almost 0.[2]

3 Proposed Algorithm

There are multiple perspectives regarding the need for a better algorithm.

- Log-network has complex output for certain types of input.
- Do we need an activation function given that log itself is non-linear? i.e., log itself acts as an activation layer. Also, if there are two log layers, the bottom one is an approximate linear layer if we use hashing and the top one is an activation layer.
- The bias and weight 2D "image" acts like an indirect loss landscape. Can we use this to explain the predictions?
- We are assuming that w is larger than x . So, the sign of output of $\log(x + w)$ should be the sign of w . (instead of dealing with complex numbers)
- If we have one grayscale 2D image X , then, for the same shape, we need to have W . Then, we should do $\log(X + W)$ before we do integral image. This represents one single image channel and one single weight kernel.
- **For multiple kernels, use multiple W matrices.** [6] For a 3 channel image, consider 4D weight matrix. 0th axis along rows, 1st axis along columns, 2nd axis along input channels and 3rd axis along output channels. [For Bias matrix, it will be the same, but, 2nd axis will have 1 item always] Then, the output will be along 2nd axis with bias being a scalar for each kernel position. So, integral image is supposed to be done using 0 and 1 axes.
- This hierarchy of localised features may work better for diverse data. For example, if there is only one small object in a large image, then, for object detection, the network may have to learn lot of negative samples if we do it like that of Convolution Neural Network (<https://pytorch.org/docs/stable/nn.html#convolution-layers>).[4]
- ReLU is not needed. But, it makes the architecture easier. So, the experiments should include both ReLU and non-ReLU versions.
- max-pooling or average-pooling may be needed to reduce the size of the output. (padding is recommended for "receptive field")
- **We need to be cautious when using even sized kernels** Backpropagation can cause half-pixel shift if these even sized kernels use "middle pixel" for aggregation.
- Predictions can be explained by showing 25 to 75 percentile color map of both weight and bias matrices.
- All experiments may be run using IILN, MNIST and CPU.[5]

- If x is the input, w is the weight, y is the output, $\frac{\partial L}{\partial w} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial y} \times \frac{1}{x+w} = \frac{\frac{\partial L}{\partial y}}{x+w}$
 - So, $x + w$ should not be 0. $|x + w| < \epsilon \Rightarrow x + w = 1$
 - Similarly, $|x + w| > t \Rightarrow x + w = t$. The use of this "t" condition depends on the floating point instructions of the particular computer architecture.
- Max-pooling or average pooling or stride greater than 1 or sampling in the initial layers can be used to make sure that the minor problems related to different aspect ratios and different cameras are taken care of.
- Backpropagation receptive field shape is same as that of kernel for stride = 1, dilation = 1 and default conditions.

References

- [1] Prasad N R. *Probabilistic Representation: Additive Statically Approximate Distributions*. Zenodo, 9 June 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11529370>.
- [2] Rumelhart, D., Hinton, G. and Williams, R. *Learning representations by back-propagating errors*. Nature 323, 533–536 (1986).
- [3] Franklin C Crow, *Summed-Area Tables for Texture mapping*, Computer Sciences Laboratory, Xerox Palo Alto Research Center, Computer Graphics, Siggraph, ACM, Volume 18, Number 3 (July 1984).
- [4] [LeCun et al., 1998a] Y. LeCun, L. Bottou, Y. Bengio, and P. Haffner. "Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition." Proceedings of the IEEE, 86(11):2278-2324, November 1998.
- [5] <http://yann.lecun.com/exdb/mnist/>
 "THE MNIST DATABASE of handwritten digits" Yann LeCun et. al.
- [6] Harris, C.R., Millman, K.J., van der Walt, S.J. et al. *Array programming with NumPy*. Nature 585, 357–362 (2020).